

Time Average Impulse and New Probability Conservation in One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

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If one considers an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction junction) with p_1 in n_1 and p_2 in n_2 , but energy the same in both, it seems that there would be an issue with the idea of action-reaction. For instance, if one gives a weight A to p_1 and C to p_2 , then $Ap_1 = Cp_2$ would imply that $A > C$. The question is: What does this weight mean if there is only one photon? One cannot balance A with C and Ap_1 with Ap_2 at the same time. It seems that one needs to introduce the idea of a reflected photon, with weight B , which has momentum $-p_1$ for E to be the same. Then, one may try to introduce a time averaged impulse balance. One might at first think of $A=1$ and B and C being probabilities in a classical sense. An issue arises if one wishes to create balance based on space. A time averaged scenario means that time is removed from the picture and that the reflected and incident photons appear together on the LHS and the refracted on the RHS.

The main point is that with such a balance, A must be reduced by B in order to create $A > C$. In other words, $B < 0$ at the junction point. As a result, B cannot be a usual classical probability. A negative B , however, means that the time averaged impulse balance is: $Ap_1 + (-p_1)(-|B|) = Cp_2$. Thus, there is a negative B probability which is required to remove some of A , but at the same time reverses the impulse sign of $-p_1$. Thus, one uses a new set of probabilities in a time removed picture which account for probability removal (or augmentation) together with momentum removal or augmentation such that one has a balance for both on the LHS and RHS. Thus, this new probability is intertwined with momentum.

We argue that one may link these ideas with $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length and obtain $\exp(ipx)$ as the new unusual probability if one insists on momentum conservation.

Probability Which Ensures Conservation of Momentum and Removes Time

In (1), we suggested one may obtain the free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, by seeking a probability which conserved momentum. This requires $F(p_1)F(p_2) = F(p_1+p_2)$ in one dimension and must somehow have $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$ yield probability=1 and $p_1+p_2 \neq p_3+p_4$ (one dimension), probability 0. To do so, one needs to use $-p_3-p_4$ for the final momentum and introduce an extra variable x to create orthogonal functions which are 0 when integrated over x in the case of no momentum conservation.

In a second note (2), we argued that p is a dynamic variable which does not require a clock for its measurement, only impulse. We then suggested creating a probability scheme which does not use time and again obtained $\exp(ipx)$.

Here we ask: How is the notion of no time (clock present) useful? We suggest that one consider the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction. An incident photon with momentum p_1 may either become a reflected photon with $-p_1$ or a refracted one with p_2 . The point is that E (energy) is the same for all and one would expect a kind of impulse balance in a time averaged sense. This then, would be an example of a situation which requires a probability scheme with

no time present. We wish to investigate this in more detail in a classical sense and see that usual classical ideas break down with respect to probability.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

We suggested above a time-averaged impulse balance for a one dimensional reflection-refraction, but at the same time one uses probabilities in an average and these must be balanced as well. We first consider a p_1 moving to the right and suddenly becoming $p_2 > p_1$ at x_0 with E (energy) remaining constant. This appears like a net force is applied to change p_1 to p_2 , but no work is done because E is constant. It would seem that one would like to have an impulse balance, with impulse proportional to p and E the same in all cases. This seems to imply a reflected photon with momentum $-p_1$. Given that there are probabilities for a photon to reflect and refract and that these occur at different times, we suggest a time averaged picture which uses space, i.e. the incident and reflected photon are on the LHS of x_0 and the refracted on the RHS. The time averaging places the incident and reflected photons on the LHS side together and leads to altogether different probability than the usual classical one. The issue is that A and B appear on the LHS and represent probabilities at different times. In a time averaged picture, however, they are together, and B needs to reduce A if C is less than A in a classical scheme.

One way to see that C may be less than A is to consider momentum. If A is a probability linked to p_1 and C to p_2 , then $A p_1$ and $C p_2$ represent average probabilities at x_0 , so for $p_2 > p_1$, $C < A$. Probability itself, however, should be conserved and this cannot occur for $A = C$. Thus, one needs an extra piece, namely a reflected ray. In this probability scheme, however, for $C < A$, B , the reflected "probability" must diminish A . This is a negative probability and so reverses the sign of $-p_1$ when multiplied by it. Thus, probability and average impulse are intertwined.

. This negative probability (in a scheme with no time i.e. time averaged) has the added feature of reducing A , i.e. $A + B < A$ and $A + B = C$. Thus, A, B, C act like a kind of conserved probability, but B is negative and serves to reduce A (for $p_1 < p_2$), but at the same time reverses the sign of $(-p_1)$ in $B(-p_1)$ in order that the incident and reflected photons represent impulses in the same direction.

As a result, matters are different in a probability scheme linked to impulse conservation with time removed. We suggest that impulse conservation is akin to momentum conservation. This possibly positive or negative probability should also account for momentum conservation. In addition, a particle with constant p should be associated with constant probability in space, i.e. $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length. This does not allow for positive or negative values, but a two dimensional oscillating function does and its magnitude is a constant, i.e. $1/L$.

It is still not clear what the arguments of this function should be, but if one wishes to have a probability associated with momentum conservation, then:

$$F(p_1)F(p_2) = F(p_1 + p_2) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{one-dimension}$$

This suggests $\exp(ipx)$ as the probability function, but this requires integration over x and $-p_3 - p_4$ for final momenta states together with $p_1 + p_2$.

The point we wish to make is that an $\exp(ipx)$ function linked with momentum conservation also does not consider time as one uses $-p_3-p_4$ to show a later time. The continuity of this $\exp(ipx)$ scheme and its first derivative is equivalent to a time averaged unusual probability $A+B=C$ and impulse balance $A(p_1) - p_1B=Cp_2$. Thus, the balance is done with coefficients which are not the usual classical probabilities of 1 for an incident photon and $P(\text{reflected})$, $P(\text{refracted})$. These probabilities A,B,C nonetheless allow for a reduction in A (for $p_1 < p_2$) and change the sign of $B(-1)$ so that the reflected and incident photons have the same impulse direction to the left, so that there is an augmented impulse matching the time averaged impulse to the right for Cp_2 . Thus, A,B,C are probabilities associated with impulse and momentum conservation.

What if $p_1 > p_2$? There should be a net impulse direction to the left in the p_2 region because p_1 is slowed down. If one has Ap_1 , then $B(-p_1)$ with $B > 0$, ensures that there is momentum to the left. Given $A+B=C$ with $B > 0$, $C > 0$, then $A < C$.

From (3), one may see actual values:

$$B/A = (p_1 - p_2) / (p_1 + p_2) \quad \text{and} \quad C/A = 2p_1 / (p_1 + p_2) \quad ((2))$$

For $p_2 > p_1$, $B < 0$. For $p_2 < p_1$, simply considering Ap_1 and Cp_2 means that $C > A$ so B must be positive to augment A . The full expression ((2)) shows also that $C > A$ for $p_2 < p_1$. In terms of impulse, one has for $A=1$, p_1 with $(-p_1)(p_1 - p_2) / (p_1 + p_2)$ where $(p_1 - p_2) / (p_1 + p_2)$ is less than 1, but still positive. This means that on the LHS side has partially canceling time averaged impulses. Thus, probabilities $A+B$ augment, but average impulses on the LHS partially cancel.

The fact that one uses an average momentum balance (even though it is time averaged) means that momentum balance or conservation is important, but at the same time probability is used to create an average and probability should be conserved as well. It is this intertwining of average momentum conservation and probability which gives rise to the possibility of negative probability and ultimately leads to $\exp(ipx)$.

How is It Possible that the Same Reflected Photon May be Associated with Either Positive or Negative Average Impulse?

It is unusual that the same reflected photon with $-p_1$ may be associated with either a positive or negative impulse, but one is establishing a probability scheme with no time which shows probability removal or addition by the reflected photon (depending on whether $C > A$ or not) and this in turn is linked to a corresponding impulse balance. If probability is being removed by the reflected photon, then this is like an opposite impulse it seems.

Classical Scenario

To obtain the classical picture for one dimensional reflection-refraction, one may combine $A+B=C$ and $A(p_1) + B(-p_1)=Cp_2$ to obtain: $AAp_1 = BBp_1 + CCp_2$. If one tries to write this with spatial pieces together, one has; $AA(p_1) - BBp_1 = CCp_2$. In this case, AA , BB , CC are

physical fluxes (not probabilities) which are leading to a momentum type balance equation, but there is no flux balance equation here, so one is not dealing with a probability picture. One needs a probability without p as well to show a related probability decrease.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that if one wishes to have a probability scheme which removes time and is consistent with momentum conservation, then one must mix probabilities and average impulses which occur at different times. This means that one requires a probability of a reflected photon which may decrease the “probability” of the incident photon if $p_2 > p_1$. This is akin to reversing the impulse direction of $-p_1$ (i.e. this is combined with negative probability). In other words, one must consider a probability balance together with a time averaged momentum or impulse balance. In the case of $p_1 > p_2$, the reflected photon is associated with probability which enhances the “probability” of the incident photon, but leads to partial impulse cancellation.

Thus, in short, the quantum mechanics of using $\exp(ipx)$ leads to a probability with time removed, but with a new probability which is conserved together with average momentum or impulse as seen in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. Thus the two key ideas are probability and average momentum or impulse conservation, but negative probabilities may occur because objects occurring at different times are placed together in an equation. In other words, one object may ultimately remove or use up part of the probability of the initial probability and this object would appear with a negative probability. This negative probability is like a positive probability which shows up at a later time, but there is no time in this picture.

References

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